

Revus

Revija za ustavno teorijo in filozofijo prava

56 | 2025

Varia

Quid jus or quid juris?

Law, the law, and the point of legal philosophy

Mathieu Carpentier

Electronic version

URL: <https://journals.openedition.org/revus/11964>

DOI: 10.4000/15r3e

ISSN: 1855-7112

Publisher

Klub Revus

Electronic reference

Mathieu Carpentier, "*Quid jus or quid juris?*", *Revus* [Online], 56 | 2025, Online since 23 February 2026, connection on 16 March 2026. URL: <http://journals.openedition.org/revus/11964> ; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/15r3e>

This text was automatically generated on March 16, 2026.

The text only may be used under licence CC BY-SA 4.0. All other elements (illustrations, imported files) may be subject to specific use terms.

Quid jus or quid juris?

Law, the law, and the point of legal philosophy

Mathieu Carpentier

Law - nobody knows what it is
Gustave Flaubert

- 1 This article will defend a seemingly simple claim: what law is (*quid jus*) and what the law is in a given jurisdiction (*quid juris*) are two separate questions, the answers to which depend on the success of two different intellectual endeavours. In a nutshell, lawyers, judges, and jurists are concerned with ascertaining *what the law is* or *requires* in their jurisdiction (or in other jurisdictions if they are comparativists, or in the same jurisdiction but in the past, if they are legal historians). Legal theorists and philosophers try to articulate a concept (or at least a conception) of *what law is*. Lawyers do not need to settle debates about the “nature of law” to do their jobs. Disagreements (among lawyers) about what the law is do not track or match disagreements (among legal philosophers) about what law is. Of course, the way judges and lawyers ascertain what the law is (or requires)—which I will call *quid juris* ascertainments, QJurAs for short—is far from irrelevant for legal philosophers because QJurAs are part of the practice legal philosophers seek to investigate. So, legal philosophers will debate whether QJurAs ever mobilise moral evaluation, for instance. But these debates are *conceptual*: they are about the concept (or conception) of QJurA entailed by a philosopher’s concept (or conception) of law. They are not *empirical* debates about the way lawyers in a given jurisdiction do QJurAs; nor are there *legal/normative* debates about the proper way to do QJurAs in a given jurisdiction.
- 2 Now, the *quid jus/quid juris* distinction was already articulated long ago by Immanuel Kant in the *Rechtslehre*:

Like the much-cited query ‘what is truth?’ put to the logician, the question ‘what is Law?’ might well embarrass the jurist if he does not want to lapse into a tautology or, instead of giving a universal solution, refer to what the laws in some country at some time prescribe. He can indeed state what is laid down as the law (*quid sit iuris*), that is, what the laws in a certain place and at a certain time say or have said. (Kant 1991: 55)¹

- 3 Of course, Kant does not characterize the *quid jus* endeavour in the same terms that many of his successors would: for instance, Kant sees the *quid jus* question as a mixed conceptual/normative question (e.g., whether law's directives conform with right reason), rather than a strictly conceptual one. Be that as it may, I think the distinction is both important and meaningful.
- 4 This is why I keep finding myself puzzled by the fact that this distinction is lost in many parts of contemporary jurisprudence. Ever since Dworkin introduced "theoretical disagreements" as a specific challenge to legal positivism, jurisprudential discourse has often confused questions about law with questions about the law; and even those jurists who agree with the distinction nevertheless insist that ascertaining what the law is (or requires) ultimately depends on what law is (something I will call the "dependence view"). The appeal of such a view is evident: if, to do QJurAs on a daily basis, judges and lawyers have to turn to philosophical truths about law, then it makes legal philosophy eminently *relevant* to legal practice, especially at a time when claims to such relevance are met with increased scepticism.² And the essentialist overtones of many writings on the "nature of law"—as being made up of "essential" or "necessary" properties—can be redeemed if they prove useful to legal practice.
- 5 As appealing as this quest for relevance may be, it is nevertheless ill-founded. In this paper, I will defend the commonplace view that questions about what law is and questions about what the law is should be kept distinct. One unfortunate upshot of this defence is that it calls into question the very point of doing legal philosophy: if it is not relevant for legal practice, especially in QJurA matters, what is it good for?³
- 6 Three important caveats before we start.
- 7 (1) By "legal philosophy", I will mean throughout something like "general jurisprudence", that is the philosophical investigation of the concept of law—or the "nature of law", whatever one thinks that is—as well as many other related questions. I take general jurisprudence to be an important, almost foundational, subfield of legal philosophy. But many other subfields of legal philosophy may prove relevant for legal practice, especially "special jurisprudence" (that is, the philosophy of specific areas of law), but also normative jurisprudence, feminist jurisprudence, critical race theory, etc. I will not focus on these specific subfields in this paper.
- 8 (2) This paper is not a polemic *against* legal philosophy, understood as an inquiry into the "nature of law". Quite the contrary. The only point this paper will try to make is that *whatever relevance* legal philosophy has, it does not come from its relevance to legal practice: in other words, whatever relevance the philosophical discussion of the nature of law and/or of the concept of law (*quid jus*) has, it is not predicated on its relevance for ascertaining what the law is or requires in a given context. And this holds whatever your conception of the "nature" or the "concept" of something is. I do not plan to rehearse the debates relating to essentialism v. anti-essentialism in legal philosophy,⁴ nor settle any meta-philosophical debate about what philosophical inquiries about the nature or the concept of law are really about. So, it does not change much for present purposes whether you aim to answer the question "what law is" by trying to retrieve law's essential properties (Raz 2009: 92; but see, refuting the "essentialist" label, Raz 2007: 118)—or by elucidating the focal meaning of law (Finnis 2011)—or through constructive conceptual explanation (Giudice 2015)—or through reductionism (Marmor 2013)—or through "ordinary analysis" (Chiassoni 2011), etc.

- 9 (3) This is not a paper on theory versus practice. I certainly do not mean to deny that law, as a practice, is theory-laden. Ascertaining what the law is or requires (*quid juris*) does rest on what, following Felipe Jiménez, I will call in the last section of this paper an “image of law”, that is, an inchoate, often un-expressed concept of law. I also accept that legal philosophy is deeply (and somewhat unacknowledgedly) informed by the jurisprude’s underlying “image of law”, and that, to some extent, the jurisprude’s work in establishing what law is must rest on a shared “foundational folk theory” (Dyrda and Gizbert-Studnicki 2022). I have no qualms in accepting that “our concept of law constitutes the reality of law” (Sciaraffa 2011: 2). That being said, the only claim this paper is going to make is that, whatever inchoate “concept of law” is part and parcel of the deep conceptual structure of QJurAs in a given jurisdiction, elucidating this deep conceptual structure, and *a fortiori* sharing a philosophical concept of *what law is* (*quid jus*) is not necessary for ascertaining *what the law is*. The theory-ladenness of legal practice does not make legal philosophy relevant (or *a fortiori* necessary) for law-ascertainment practices. Therefore, legal disputes, that is, disagreements about what the law is (or requires),⁵ do not typically (or ever) revolve around a disagreement about what law is. Or so I will claim in this paper.

1 Persistent confusions

- 10 In this section, I will try to show that confusions between *what law is* and *what the law is* (or requires) are pervasive and cut across the usual divides (especially between legal positivists and anti-positivists). Dworkin bears a huge responsibility for this situation, as he originated the confusion. However many positivists, instead of calling him out on it, adopted the confusion wholesale and made it their own. That’s on them.
- 11 Let me be clear, though. The distinction between *law* (the social phenomenon or set of social phenomena we call law) and *the law* (the set of rules, rights, obligations, powers etc. that exist in a given jurisdiction) is not specifically positivistic, as some may have argued.⁶ To the contrary, some leading natural lawyers have claimed it as their own, beginning with John Finnis.⁷
- 12 My aim is not to provide an exhaustive overview of all the ways the confusion has crept into the existing literature. I am, instead, going to take three examples to illustrate a more general point.

1.1 “Theoretical” disagreements and the Semantic Sting

- 13 In *Law’s Empire* (Dworkin 1986: 4), Dworkin⁸ claims that what makes propositions of law—such as “no cruel and unusual punishments shall be inflicted” or “Smith owes Jones \$25”—true or false is what he calls the “grounds of law”. Grounds of law are the propositions in virtue of which propositions of law are true. For instance, if facts about legislative activity are deemed grounds of law in a legal system, then propositions of law will be true in that system if, and only if, past pronouncements of the legislature make them true, e.g., if the statute book “contains” such a law. Lawyers may disagree about what the statute book says, in which case we have what Dworkin calls an empirical disagreement. But, as Dworkin claims, more often than not disagreements among lawyers about the truth of propositions of law are not empirical: they are theoretical. Theoretical disagreements are about grounds of law: the disagreement is

not whether a given “ground” makes a given proposition of law true or false, it is about what should count as a ground of law, in other words, what should count as a truth-maker for legal propositions. For instance, in the (in)famous *Riggs v. Palmer*⁹ case, the disagreement among the majority of the N.Y. Court of Appeals and the dissenter was ultimately about what counted as a ground for the proposition “Elmer Palmer may (or may not) inherit”: the judges in the majority used a principled approach to statutory intention, whereas the dissenting judge argued that what constituted “the statute” applicable to the case was the literal meaning of the statutory case. Hence their disagreement was “theoretical” and not “empirical” (Dworkin 1986: 15-20).

- 14 As you may have already guessed, I disagree (and my disagreement certainly is theoretical!). I think the disagreement in *Riggs* was squarely “empirical”¹⁰ because it is an interpretative disagreement about the meaning of the statute, that is, about what the statute required, given potentially conflicting norms (such as the common law principle according to which no man can profit from his own wrong). This is the bread and butter of adjudication, and nothing in it hangs on the nature of the “grounds” of law (whatever they are): all the members of the panel in *Riggs* seemed to agree that whatever the statute means, it is at least part of the truth-makers of the legal proposition “Elmer may (or may not) inherit”. Fortunately, Dworkin has a rejoinder to people like me: we are adherents to an implausible view of law, which he calls the “plain-fact view” (Dworkin 1986: 6-9). This view holds that law exists as a plain-fact, its existence being independent of what it should be. Whenever it runs out, then judges must rely on their views about what law should be because they are called upon to exercise discretion.
- 15 According to Dworkin, such a view is implausible because it rests on a “semantic theory of law”, which aims to provide a “criterial” explanation of the concept “law”. This is, in a nutshell, the “Semantic Sting agreement” (Dworkin 1986: 31-44). According to semantic theories, the very meaning of the word “law” rests on shared criteria of application: “Semantic theories suppose that lawyers and judges use mainly the same criteria (though these are hidden and unrecognized) in deciding when propositions of law are true or false” (Dworkin 1986: 33). Of course, semantic theorists will disagree about these shared criteria. But these disagreements do not need to trickle down onto lawyers and judge, since all theorists presuppose shared agreement on a given set of criteria of application of the concept (or the word) “law”. An Austinian will presuppose that all lawyers call “law” whatever the sovereign commands; a Hartian will argue that what lawyers call “law” is instead the set of rules identified as “law” by the rule of recognition etc. But according to Dworkin, semantic theories are unable to understand how lawyers could disagree about the very criteria of application of the concept-word “law”. He agrees, “If two lawyers are actually following *different* rules in using the word ‘law’, using different factual criteria to decide when a proposition of law is true or false... they are only talking past each other” (Dworkin 1986: 43-44). This conclusion of “semantic theories” is, according to Dworkin, “bizarre” and “wrong” and it presents law as a “grotesque joke”.
- 16 Now, there have been many attempts to defuse the Semantic Sting as a strawman (Hart 2012: 246-248; Raz 2009: 60-61). But I think that the clearest *coup de grâce* was provided by Jules Coleman: “we must attend to a fundamental confusion at the heart of the [Semantic Sting] argument... this is the confusion between the *content of the concept of law* and the *content of the law of a particular community*” (Coleman 2001: 180). To be quite

honest, the remainder of this paper could be a paraphrase of this quotation. So, forgive me for quoting Coleman a bit more because he is spot on:

While it is true on a criterial semantics that two individuals who follow different rules for applying the word or concept “law” must be assigning different meanings to it, it hardly follows that two people who are using different factual criteria to decide whether a proposition of law is true or false must be assigning different meanings to the term “law”, or employing different concepts of law. This simply confuses the notion of *law* with the notion of *the law* of a particular community (Coleman, 2001, 181).

- 17 This is a powerful objection¹¹ (on which, see also Levenbook 2015: 2), but in “Thirty Years On”, Dworkin dismissed it somewhat summarily: “there is an obvious and important connection between” what law is and what the law of a particular community is. “When a lawyer declares, for example, that in his jurisdiction ‘it is the law’ that price-fixing contracts are illegal, he is using the concept of law in stating the content of the law of a particular community” (Dworkin 2006: 221). But that is simply not the case. As I intend to show in section 2, the word “law” in propositions starting with “law is” and “it is the law that” can be interchanged with two distinct and irreducible sets of expressions. Besides, Dworkin cannot explain away his confusion between what *law* is and what *the law is* by simply arguing that there is an “obvious” connexion between the two, which precisely commits him to reiterating the confusion.

1.2 The dependence view

- 18 Another set of jurisprudes accept the distinction between what law is and what the law is but nevertheless argue that what the law is depends on what law is. Scott Shapiro articulates this view in *Legality*. Shapiro fully accepts the *quid jus/quid juris* distinction:

It is important to distinguish the question “What is law?” from the similar-sounding question “What is the law?” The latter is of course a familiar, garden-variety legal question. It reflects a desire to understand what the law is on a particular matter and is the kind of question a client would be likely to ask his or her lawyer. The former question, by contrast, does not concern the current state of the law. It reflects a philosophical effort to understand the nature of law in general” (Shapiro 2011: 7).

- 19 I wholeheartedly agree. But Shapiro nevertheless claims that the two questions are deeply connected. It is worth quoting him in full here:

A great deal does turn on the question of “What is Law?” In fact, I will argue that it is not possible to address many of the most pressing practical matters that concern lawyers— including who has the legal authority to regulate which conduct and how to interpret legal texts—without addressing the analytical questions that have traditionally preoccupied philosophers of law as well. (...) Analytical jurisprudence has profound practical implications for the practice of law—or, in other words, that the answer to what the law is in any particular case depends crucially on the answer to what law is in general” (Shapiro 2011: 25).

- 20 As much as I understand the urge to make analytical jurisprudence relevant for legal practice, I cannot help but remain unconvinced. The claim that it is impossible to address *quid juris* questions without ascertaining what law is, is rendered wholly implausible by the empirical fact that lawyers and judges do not usually dabble in analytical jurisprudence. Moreover, if addressing the question “what is law?” was necessary to ascertain what the law is, then Dworkin would be right that legal practice would ultimately rest on theoretical disagreements: philosophical theories about the

nature of law are rife with disagreement, “law” being probably an essentially contested concept (Spaić 2014). If knowing what law is (such as it is defined by these theories) was a necessary condition for knowing what the law is, then ordinary legal disputes would necessarily reflect the kind of theoretical disagreements that have been existing between legal philosophers for centuries. The fact that there is widespread convergence among legal officials on what the law is in their jurisdiction renders this view wholly implausible.

21 Shapiro however is adamant that

in order to prove conclusively that the law is thus-and-so in a particular jurisdiction, it is not enough to know who has authority within the jurisdiction, which texts they have approved, and how to interpret them. One must also know a general philosophical truth, namely, how legal authority and proper interpretive methodology are established in general. In other words, one must know which facts ultimately determine the existence and content of legal systems (Shapiro 2011: 25).

22 Must one, though? Is it really the case that “if one wants to demonstrate conclusively that the law is thus-and-so in any particular case, one must know certain philosophical truths about the nature of law in general”? (Ibid).

23 Now, demonstrating conclusively that the law is thus-and-so is the specific job of lawyers and judges. So, Shapiro is necessarily claiming that that lawyers and judges *know* philosophical truths about the nature of law because if such knowledge is a prerequisite for ascertaining what the law is, and since lawyers and judges routinely exercise such ascertainment, then it must be the case that they know these truths. This, however, is at best an unsupported assertion. Not only is it very unlikely that judges and lawyers have *beliefs* about philosophical truths about the nature of law, but even assuming they do, we have no way to ascertain whether they have *knowledge* of such truths, since they hardly ever openly philosophize about the nature of law. It could be the case that any beliefs they harbour about the nature of law are false. By contrast, lawyers and judges usually are able to explain what the law requires (i.e., to do QJurAs), and would be able to do so even if they had no beliefs about the nature of law or about the facts that ultimately ground legal facts, or if their beliefs were false. Of course, lawyers and judges are sometimes (often?) wrong in their QJurAs, but false beliefs about the nature of law are not usually the reason why they are wrong. It is much more plausible that one can very well know, e.g., who has legal authority in one’s jurisdiction—a routine ascertainment in most circumstances—without any idea about what makes that an instance of the concept of “legal authority”—a concept in need of philosophical explanation if there ever was one.

1.3 Eliminativism

24 In recent years, several variants of eliminativism have made the rounds in legal theory (Lewis Kornhauser, Scott Hersowitz, and Hillary Nye being eliminativism’s main exponents). I will not opine here on the merits of eliminativism as a first-order jurisprudential option, nor will I choose among the various accounts (some weaker, some stronger) of what is supposed to be eliminated in the first place. I will merely show that the confusion between law and the law lies at the heart of some strands of eliminativism. However, this doesn’t necessarily impugn its viability as a jurisprudential theory. In fact, I will claim that a clearer distinction between law and the law could strengthen the cogency of some versions of eliminativism.

- 25 For instance, Lewis Kornhauser (2015; see also Kornhauser 2004) claims that we can dispense with what he calls the “doctrinal concept of law”, in the sense Dworkin defines it in the Introduction to *Justice in Robes* (Dworkin 2006: 2): it consists in “the concept of ‘the law’ of some place or entity being to a particular effect”. Like Dworkin, Kornhauser contrasts such a concept of law with other possible concepts (sociological, taxonomic, aspirational/evaluative, as well as “the folk concept of law”). The doctrinal concept of law addresses the question “What makes a proposition of law true?” According to Kornhauser, we can dispense with this concept insofar as judges and other law-apppliers need not have a concept of law to apply the reasons (be they legal or non-legal) that apply to the cases at hand. All they need is to identify a set of materials (call them legal materials) that will provide guidance on how to decide cases: they do not need to “find law” as it were. It seems that what Kornhauser has in mind is eliminating the concept of *quid juris* (what the law is). Although he suggests that social science could do with a descriptive/taxonomic concept of law (which I take to be roughly equivalent to a *quid jus* concept), this appears to be a distinct kind of eliminativism (see Kornhauser 2004). Does that mean that Kornhauser is clear about the distinction between law and the law? I do not think so. First, like Dworkin, he supposes that the various “concepts” of law are concepts of the *same thing*, which differ mainly depending on the intellectual endeavours of the people using the concept. Second—and as a consequence—he suggests that a “descriptive/taxonomic” concept of law necessarily entails a “doctrinal concept”: “the correct identification of the doctrinal concept of law is central to philosophers of law” (Kornhauser 2015: 14). So, according to Kornhauser, from e.g., an exclusive positivist point of view, the exclusion of moral facts from determinants of legality is a crucial component of what the law is in a given society. As I intend to show in the next section, this assertion is unwarranted.
- 26 Another example can be taken from the work of Hillary Nye, perhaps the most sophisticated and philosophically robust exponent of eliminativism today (Nye 2022). Nye’s eliminativism is primarily meta-philosophical. Consistent with her earlier writings on the topic (Nye 2017), she claims that legal philosophy should just stop trying to investigate the “nature of law”. To some extent, I agree. An important part of her argument regarding why we should eliminate “law” as an object for metaphysical investigation is that it makes no difference in practice (Nye 2022: 50ff). Again, I completely agree (unsurprisingly). However, Nye remains to some extent prisoner of a very specific framing the dispute, put forward by Dworkinian non-eliminativists such as Liam Murphy (2014: 73-108). Nye claims that the debate between e.g., legal positivists and natural lawyers, as well as among positivists (exclusive and inclusive), is a debate about the “grounds of law”, which she seems to assume is essential to the quest for “the nature of law” and is therefore part of the stuff to be eliminated. The problem is that there are two ways to understand “grounds of law” in this context: first, as a set *quid juris* determinants (the stuff that makes propositions of law true); second, as a set of metaphysical determinants of law for a specific part of reality (as e.g., a set of norms, or the source of normative reasons of some kind). This ambiguity weakens her position, especially as she espouses eliminativism as the claim “that we can do away with this disagreement about the grounds of law, and that we can therefore get by without answering the question of what law, or the law, is” (Nye 2022: 50, emphasis added). This equation between law and the law commits her to taking Murphy’s objection to eliminativism seriously, namely, that “we need a view about the grounds of law if we are to be able to figure out the content of the law in force”

(Murphy 2014: 77). But she fails to realise that Murphy’s admonition rests either on a tautology or a non-sequitur. If by “grounds of law” we mean “what the law is on such-and-such issue”, then it means the same as “the content of the law in force” (hence the tautology); if by “grounds of law” we mean *what law is* as a metaphysical object, then it is by no means the case that a view about the grounds of law is a prerequisite for figuring out the content of the law in force (hence the non-sequitur). Because she fails to point out this ambiguity, Nye commits a form of *quid juris* eliminativism, by claiming that when we try to figure out what the law is, we use “law” as a placeholder for another idea (e.g., “what would judges do—or be bound to do—if I φ ?”). In my opinion, Nye’s position would be stronger if she distinguished between eliminativism about law and eliminativism about *the law*, and commit only to the former¹², as endorsing the latter is not a necessary consequence thereof.

2 *Quid juris* ascertainties and legal disagreements

- 27 So far, I have provided an incomplete picture of where the distinction between law (*quid jus*) and the law (*quid juris*) lies. I have mainly underscored the many ways in which leading jurisprudences of our time sometimes ignore this distinction. In this section I will try to articulate the *pars construens* of this paper and explain why theories about what law is are not relevant to QJurAs *even though* QJurAs are part of the object theorized.

2.1 The fallacy

- 28 The gist of the argument is the following. The confusion I have tried to underscore ultimately rests on a fallacy. The fallacy goes this way:

(1) Whatever “makes X be law” is what legal philosophers talk about when they talk about the nature of law.

(2) Competing theories: “Source-traceability makes X be law” *versus* “Moral conformity makes Y be law.”

(3) X and Y cannot be law at the same time.

(4) Lawyer A: “X is law”, *versus* Lawyer B: “Y is law.”

Ergo:

(5) Lawyer A and B disagree about the nature of law. *QED*

- 29 Where does the fallacy lie? First, as I have intimated, (1) is confused. When legal philosophers ask what *law* is, they ask what a certain social phenomenon (“law”) is and how it relates to other normative entities. In propositions starting with “law is...” and “it is the law that...”, the word “law” can be interchanged with two very different sets of expressions. Take the proposition “law is the union of primary and secondary rules”. “Law” can be interchanged with “a legal system”, “a legal order”, “*le droit*”, “*das Recht*”, or whatever expression may be used to denote (broadly) the notion of a given set of rights or obligations. Specific jurisdictions or legal systems are instances of “law” in that specific sense. Now, take the proposition “it is the law that one ought to φ ”. The

word “law” cannot be interchanged with such expressions as “a legal system” or “a legal order”. Rather, it could be replaced by “it is part of the laws of this jurisdiction that” or “it is legally required that”, etc.

- 30 This is why (2) typically conflates the *quid jus* and the *quid juris* questions. There is a crucial difference between, on the one hand, lawyers debating whether, e.g., the “no one can profit from his own wrong” rule is the law, that is, whether it is part of the laws of their system, or whether the rule’s moral merit is the reason why it is a legal rule (which is a *quid juris* disagreement) and, on the other hand, legal philosophers debating whether morality is part of a legal system’s criteria of validity. Law-ascertainment practices are indeed a big part of what law is, but all legal philosophy is concerned about is that (1) law-ascertainment practices exist, and (2) they can be *conceptualized* as either source-dependent or morality-dependent (or both). Appeal to morality by lawyers in their QJurAs will not, as I will explain further in the next subsection, be a problem for a theory about the nature of law that excludes morality from the system’s criteria of legality. Hence contrary to (4), the debate about our two lawyers is ultimately about what *the law is*. This is why (5) does not follow.
- 31 Does that mean that “law” and “the law” are two different concepts altogether? No, but they serve a different function. Let us assume that law is a social kind.¹³ As such, its existence and content ultimately depends on an intentional convergence of both the behaviour and beliefs of the members of the social group in treating a set of people as *legal authorities*, their pronouncements as *legal rules*, etc. When members of the group ascertain what the law is on φ -ing, they look at past pronouncements and directives on φ -ing as something that *counts as* the law. They act towards these pronouncements and directives as something that counts as a legal rule, and they form beliefs as to the properties that these pronouncements and directives—as well as of the people who issued them—are supposed to have to count as the law on φ -ing. This is exactly what I labelled as “QJurA”, or at least part of it.
- 32 Now, “law” refers to this social practice of giving certain pronouncements and directives the quality of laws (the quality of stuff that is part of the law of the jurisdiction). Each legal system is, thus, an instantiation of the concept of law. A theory of what law is will have to account for the general properties of the practice in a jurisdiction-independent way: for instance, the *existence*¹⁴ criteria for rules within the legal system is an important feature of law—that is, of all law-practices considered instances of the concept of law. The content of these criteria (e.g., what counts as “legislation”, or “precedent”, or “a source of law” more generally) in a given legal system is of course jurisdiction specific. It is this specific set of *quid juris* criteria that makes the practice the way it is, which is different from other law-practices, with different membership criteria. But people who are engaged in a social practice do not need to have the concept of a social practice, nor do they need to have the concepts (such as “criterion of membership”, “rule of recognition” or what have you) that theorists use to describe/conceptualize the practice.
- 33 To make analogy with an archetypal social kind, *money* exists when a group of people intend to use e.g., a piece of paper to exchange goods or services—and form beliefs as to what properties these pieces of paper need to have to count as money. For money to be part of the social world, only such attitudes are needed. Members of the group do not need to know *what money is* for money to exist. For them to treat stuff as money, they do not need to have the concept of money as it is used, e.g., by economists; and *a fortiori*

they don't need to have the concept of "social kind" or "institutional fact" as used by philosophers. The same goes for law: members of the group (lawyers, judges, ordinary citizens, etc.) do not need to know what law is to ascertain what the law is, that is, to treat X as the law of their jurisdiction.

- 34 Moreover, people can correctly ascertain what the law is even if they have wrong beliefs—or no beliefs at all—about what law is, that is about what the social practice they are engaged in is. As Searle writes in *The Construction of Social Reality*,
- the process of creation of institutional facts may proceed without the participants being conscious that it is happening according to this form... As long as people continue to recognise the X as having the Y status function, the institutional fact is created and maintained. They do not have to additionally recognise that they are so recognising, and they may hold all sorts of other false beliefs about what they are doing and why they are doing it" (Searle 1995: 47).
- 35 As I will explain in the third section, legal practice does rest on a deep conceptual structure, and there is no denying that most lawyers and officials in a given jurisdiction share some foundational folk theory about what law is. However, this underlying "concept of law" need not be made explicit within legal practice—and it is not always congruent with the philosophers' concept of law. Further, legal officials and lawyers need not have true beliefs, if any, about what law is in order to correctly ascertain what the law is. However, it is true that this inchoate concept of law is a sort of pre-theoretical *quid jus*, which allows officials and lawyers to identify their practice as an instance of law and to identify themselves as *legal* officials.
- 36 For this reason, as much as I agree with Arie Rosen that "our concept of law affects our law-related practices" (Rosen 2018: 130), I would dispute that our concept of law "determines the way we identify law and the way we ascertain its content" (ibid). If by "identifying law", we mean identifying our practices as *legal* practices, that is, as instances of law, Rosen is right: when we identify as lawyers or as legal officials, we do apply a sort of inchoate concept of law, which may very well be incomplete or wrong. However, if by identifying law, Rosen means identifying what *the law* is in our jurisdiction, then he falls prey to the fallacy I have tried to identify in this section.

2.1.2 Jurisprudential disagreements make no difference to QJurA practices

- 37 Still, you may object that jurisprudential disagreements about the nature of law are often (though not always¹⁵) disagreements about what counts as a QJurA. For instance, exclusive positivists claim that officials and members of the legal community do not use moral considerations as part of their QJurAs because morality (or moral meritoriousness) is not part of the criteria of membership (or, if you prefer, "validity") of laws within any given legal system. To the contrary, inclusive positivists insist that morality may be part of the criteria of membership of laws, so it is not impossible that officials use moral considerations to ascertain what the law is in their jurisdiction. Some anti-positivists claim that this is not only a possibility, but a necessity. (I am simplifying a lot here, but you get the picture).
- 38 You may then conclude that this necessarily commits jurisprudes who disagree about the nature of law (and especially about the nature of QJurAs) to also disagree about

what makes QJurAs correct in a given jurisdiction. For instance, Dale Smith, in his defence of a version of Dworkin’s argument from theoretical disagreement, writes:

[P]articipating in the debate between exclusive legal positivism and (some forms of) natural law theory commits legal officials to disagreeing about the criteria of legal validity in their jurisdiction, since some will be committed to claiming that morality is not a source of law while others will be committed to claiming that it (Smith 2010: 660).

- 39 I will leave aside for the moment the question whether officials are ever called upon to opine on legal-philosophical debates in their official capacity (spoiler: they aren’t), but suffice it to say that Smith’s view is consistent with his broad notion of “theoretical disagreement”, which encompasses not only disagreements among officials about the “grounds of law” but also disagreement amongst jurists about the nature of law (Smith 2010: 642).
- 40 Is Smith right that jurisprudential debates have direct relevance for jurisdiction-specific QJurAs? There is reason to doubt it. During QJurAs, lawyers and officials do not typically ask questions such as “is morality part of the criteria of validity/membership of our legal system?” Whether they *do* make morality part of the criteria of validity/membership of their legal system is a conceptual question, whose truth depends on a philosophical reconstruction of QJurA practices; but it does not straightforwardly depend on empirical data about specific QJurA practices in specific jurisdiction. As Coleman puts it: “the dispute between exclusive and inclusive positivists cannot be resolved on descriptive grounds, for the simple reason that the dispute is not a descriptive one. It is an interpretive dispute... The question is which view provides the best explanation or interpretation of the fact that moral language appears in constitutional clauses” (Coleman 2001: 109). More broadly, most legal philosophers accept that moral considerations are ubiquitous in legal practice and legal reasoning. Exclusive positivists do not deny that judges and other officials have routine recourse to moral evaluation (Raz 1994: 332-225). But this in itself tells us nothing. First, officials—especially judges—are rarely candid about their recourse to moral argument, which is often is cloaked under the appearance (or pretence) of “neutral lawfinding” (see Diamond 2025). Second, and more importantly, the philosophical question is how to make better sense of the fact that such recourse is ubiquitous? The question is precisely about whether such moral reasoning is part of QJurAs or not. Are judges still ascertaining what the law is when they use moral reasoning, or has the law run out? (or something in-between?). This is philosophical question, not a legal one.
- 41 The upshot is that the truth about what law is will typically depend on the best conceptual reconstruction of legal practices (including QJurA practices). It will not be assessed by reference to specific legal disputes about the scope and content of QJurAs in specific jurisdictions, but by the criteria of success of every philosophical endeavour (consistence, conceptual rigor, elegance, explanatory power, reflective equilibrium). Therefore, philosophical disputes about what law is have no relevance for specific QJurAs in specific jurisdictions: an “exclusive positivist” judge or a “natural lawyer” judge would probably decide cases the same way (all other things being equal). Or at least their disagreement would not be the mere reflection of underlying jurisprudential disputes. Similarly, two jurists may have strong disagreements about e.g., the legality of immoral laws and nevertheless agree on what the law is in their jurisdiction.
- 42 This last assertion may sound counterintuitive. Wouldn’t, say, a Radbruchian natural lawyer and a Hartian positivist precisely disagree on what the law was in Nazi

Germany? After all, *injusta lex non est lex* is precisely about what the law is (or isn't) in specific jurisdictions. It seems that whether it was lawful to be a grudge informer in Germany circa 1939 may to some extent depend on your jurisprudential views about the nature of law and its connexions with morality.

- 43 Things are, however, more complex. First, as Finnis rightly observed (Finnis 2011: 364), the claim that *injusta lex non est lex* amounts to a performative contradiction, since to make that claim, one must have identified the *lex* as a *lex* in the first place. So, there must at least be some kind of *prima facie* convergence on what the law is in a given jurisdiction, even if further argument regarding the validity of such law may lead to disagreement. Second, and more importantly, morally charged debates among lawyers and officials about what the law is do not track jurisprudential disputes. Hart and Radbruch were not disagreeing straightforwardly about points of German law, but about the best conceptual reconstruction of what German lawyers did post-1945. If, in jurisdiction X, judges use moral considerations in their QJurAs, the onus is on legal positivists to show why this doesn't disprove their point that morality is not part of the criteria of legality in X. For instance, they'll claim that positivism is only about *some* aspects of QJurAs (see *infra* 2.3.), or that when judges use moral considerations they are not ascertaining the law, but developing it (or even creating it).
- 44 The notion of "criterion of legality" (or membership) is a philosophical notion, not a legal one (just as my somewhat peculiar notion of "QJurA" is): it reconstructs what officials do, but it is not used by officials themselves. Let there be two post-1945 judges in Germany, Gustav and Herbert, who are called upon to rule on the case of the proverbial grudge informer. Gustav thinks that the informer acted unlawfully and ought to be convicted because the law that allowed his deeds at the time was immoral. Herbert thinks that the informer acted lawfully at the time and ought to be acquitted. There seems to be deep disagreement between Gustav and Herbert, but their disagreement is about what the law is (which may well be indeterminate). It is *not* a disagreement about whether morality is a criterion of legality (or a criterion of membership within legal systems), which is a determinate philosophical question.
- 45 You may then object that judges sometimes cite legal philosophers or discuss philosophical concepts in their rulings. Dworkin has been cited in several court decisions in the U.S. and Canada, and the U.K. Supreme Court discussed the "rule of recognition" at length in the *Miller (1)* case.¹⁶ But, this does not mean that whatever Dworkin or Hart had to say about the nature or the concept of law was relevant to the solution of the case. For instance, the Appellate Division of the High Court of Southern Rhodesia famously invoked the Kelsenian *Grundnorm* in the *Madzimbamuto* case¹⁷ (as did courts in Pakistan and Ouganda). But this mere fact does not show that Kelsen's theory of the nature of law (and, in this case, his ideas about the change in the *Grundnorm* during revolutionary periods) provided a dispositive account of what the law governing the solution of the case was. It shows, instead, that judges sometimes feel the urge to dabble in legal philosophy because some aspect of the case raises an interesting philosophical question; it may also be the case that the authority and prestige of someone like Kelsen provides cover, if not sheer window-dressing, for judicial lawmaking. When the *Madzimbamuto* case was heard by the Privy Council, Lord Reid wrote for the majority: "The authorities upon which [the Rhodesian Court] sought to rely, namely Kelsen [and others], may afford an accurate jurisprudential analysis of a

change in the basic laws of a country but they are not authorities upon which an English court should act.”¹⁸ He was right.

2.3 Sources of legal disagreement

- 46 Almost everybody agrees that legal practice is rife with disagreement. All over the world, Supreme Court Justices write scathing dissents and law professors attack each other’s views over hundreds of law review pages. After all, litigation is at the heart of legal practices: law is meant to settle disputes, and it is only natural that part of the dispute be about what the law is in the first place.
- 47 This is why, although there is usually a great deal of convergence around settled methods and techniques for identifying what the law is, there may still be room for disagreement among officials. This is because QJurAs are not always straightforward; they often involve argumentative and interpretive techniques, which make it an illusion to claim that what the law is on this or that issue is altogether fixed. Moreover, disagreement about the law may take many forms because the answer to the question *quid juris* is usually the result of the interplay of many different variables.
- 48 Here are some of the main sources of disagreement about the law, each resulting from a different variable:
- 49 a) *Disputes about validity/membership*. In some instances, lawyers and officials may disagree about whether a given rule is part of the legal system. There is usually strong convergence among members of the group on the criteria of membership, which are picked out by the rule of recognition (RoR). Since the RoR is meant to solve what Hart identifies as an epistemic defect—uncertainty—of systems of primary rules (Hart 2012: 94), it usually provides enough convergence among members of the group to keep disagreement at a minimum. Whenever a specific set of facts obtains (e.g., a bill is passed by Parliament and enacted by the Head of State), there is usually widespread agreement that the rules that can be traced back to those facts are legal rules. But, as Hart, noticed, the RoR is open-textured (Hart 2012: 147-154). This is especially the case during revolutionary periods, when the system of sources of law is upended. There is usually a period of deep uncertainty as to which facts must obtain for there to be legal rules. It is also sometimes the case that even in “normal” periods, participants disagree about the exact content of their RoR. A good example is custom—e.g., in international law. Everybody agrees that a rule becomes a law when it is both commonly practiced by the relevant actors (e.g., states in international law) and subject to their *opinio juris*. However, the exact threshold often is disputed: for how long must practice be settled? By how many states? What form must *opinio juris* take (especially when one is dealing with institutional actors whose mental states are inherently opaque)? These disputes often result in deep controversies as to the very existence of customary laws.¹⁹ In systems where legislation (*lato sensu*, including constitutional legislation and administrative rule-making) is paramount *qua* source of law, such disagreements may be less frequent, but they are by no means impossible. For instance, there is disagreement among members of the American legal community regarding whether the Equal Rights Amendment is part of the Constitution²⁰— although the naysayers seem to be in the majority. This is a classic case of what Hart called “uncertainty in the rule of recognition”.

- 50 b) *Interpretive disputes*. In many instances, people disagree in good faith about the meaning of legal provisions, that is, about the very content of the rule expressed by legal texts. Those are interpretive disputes, which are in part the result of the indeterminacy of legal language (vagueness, ambiguity, open texture, etc.) and the opacity of the linguistic context of enactment. Lawyers and judges, though agreeing that cruel and unusual punishments are unlawful in the U.S. (under the Eighth Amendment to the Constitution), will nevertheless disagree about the meaning of “cruel and unusual”. “Cruel” is a “thick” moral concept, the content of which may vary according to context; “unusual” can be understood temporally (“has not been usual up to now”) or spatially (“is not usual in most places”). All these features will typically trigger much disagreement among officials and lawyers.²¹ The lack of convergence among good faith speakers on the meaning of such terms will entail much disagreement about their denotation (is the death penalty a cruel and unusual punishment?).
- 51 Moreover, interpretive disputes are not only discrete disputes about the meaning of specific provisions. They often have a systemic character because members of the group typically disagree on methods and theories of legal interpretation. To take another example from the U.S., living constitutionalists, moral readers, and originalists do not disagree on the meaning of specific constitutional provisions but over the very methods that should be used to interpret all constitutional provisions; the same goes for textualists, intentionalists, and purposivists in statutory interpretation.
- 52 c) *Concretization disputes*. Sometimes participants roughly agree on the meaning of legal provisions but they are formulated at such a level of generality that implementing them means creating intermediate steps to assess whether they apply and to which cases. When people disagree about these steps we have what could be called a concretization dispute. Some would perhaps call them “construction disputes”. So, for instance, many people will agree that the Second Amendment²² to the U.S. Constitution creates a right to bear arms (though some disagree, especially those who think that the right to bear arms is limited to the well-regulated militia). They usually also agree that such a right is not absolute and may be lawfully restricted. So, whatever dispute exists among them is not interpretive *per se*. Instead, they bear of the kind of test used to assess whether a restriction to the right to bear arms is lawful. Some will advance a “tradition and history” test, which will considerably narrow the set of permissible restrictions, while others will argue that a “compelling interest” test, giving more leeway to regulators, should be upheld.²³ (I’m simplifying a lot here but bear with me). More generally, disputes over tiers of scrutiny or about specific legal doctrines (for instance the doctrine of “necessary in a democratic society” restrictions of free speech in ECtHR jurisprudence, or the “major questions doctrine” in U.S. law) are often instances of concretization disputes.
- 53 d) *Balancing disputes*. Sometimes the dispute does not fall into any of the aforementioned categories. People agree that a given law belongs to the legal system; they agree on its content, on its scope, and on the tests used to establish infringement. But sometimes whatever right or obligation it creates ought to be balanced with other rights and obligations created by other norms. Such is often the case in constitutional adjudication: when balancing is needed between two constitutional rights, disagreement among good faith actors is bound to happen. Whatever the mathematical formula used to analytically frame what is at stake in such balancing (Alexy 2021:

154-174²⁴; Duarte 2021), most balancing situations will yield disputes. When balancing, e.g., the right to privacy with the freedom of the press or environmental rights with the freedom to conduct a business or property rights, two different courts, or even two different judges on the same panel, may reasonably differ.

- 54 The upshot is: there are many ways in which QJurAs may be controversial, depending on which aspect of QJurAs is at stake. Of course, these various kinds of disputes are often combined, and there certainly are many more types of disagreement (I have not endeavoured to provide an exhaustive typology). But at no point is ascertaining *what law is* (what the nature or concept of law is) relevant to solving any of these disputes over what the law is.
- 55 Legal philosophers can easily account for some disputes, but not necessarily for others, depending on which aspect of QJurAs they deem most relevant for their account of the nature of law. For instance, legal positivists can easily account for the role morality plays in interpretive or concretization disputes, while having to explain why seemingly morally laden disputes about membership do not entail that morality be part of the criteria of membership. When establishing “what the law is” (that is, when making QJurAs), lawyers and officials have recourse to an array of considerations: about the pedigree of the rule (its membership), its applicability, its meaning, the way it can be concretized into workable tests for infringement, the way the rights and obligations it creates must be weighed against other rights and obligations. Establishing what the law is is the result of various intellectual operations, each potentially rife with disagreement. Legal philosophical disputes about the nature of law usually focus on *some aspects* of QJurAs. For instance, I have claimed in my previous work that the dispute between legal positivists and their opponents is best understood as a dispute about criteria of membership, rather than a dispute about *all* the determinants of what the law is (Carpentier 2026 channelling Gardner 2001). Different meta-philosophies of law would certainly draw different boundaries. But not all aspects of QJurAs need to be relevant for philosophical treatment. Moreover, philosophical treatments of each relevant aspect are certainly orthogonal to one another. For instance, the various debates among philosophers of legal interpretation are mostly orthogonal to the disputes between positivists and their opponents.

3 The irrelevance of legal philosophy?

- 56 Although QJurAs are an important part of law practices about which jurists philosophize, it must be clear by now that legal philosophy has no legal relevance: the way people do QJurAs does not depend on philosophical truths, but on the various criteria of correctness provided by their own legal system. This, in turn, raises the question: what is the point of legal philosophy if it is wholly irrelevant to legal practice? This is the question I want to address to conclude.
- 57 One way to redeem legal philosophy is to claim that questions about the nature of law ought not to be understood as merely conceptual: they have practical, moral import. In sum, it would be morally good if lawyers and officials adopted a given concept of law, as it is expounded by a given jurisprudential tradition. For many years normative positivists²⁵ have claimed that positivism is best understood as a normative claim about what law ought to be and the way legal actors ought to behave.

- 58 The most cogent and sophisticated defence of such a view in recent years has been put forward by Felipe Jiménez (2023). Jiménez’s paper is an exercise in what he calls conceptual prescription, in which he argues that it would be preferable if officials and lawyers adopted a positivistic concept of law. Jiménez makes it clear that what he has in mind is not what he calls a “foundational concept” of law (capturing the “constitutive features” of the object) but an “operative concept” (Jiménez 2023: 361-362), by which he means a concept that governs representational practices regarding a certain object at a given time. His claim is that operative concepts, insofar as they underlie our shared epistemic and representational practices, are ripe for conceptual engineering: if an operative concept is shared by epistemic agents but nevertheless flawed, then it can be made better, and philosophers are here to help. There may be various kinds of reasons for such flaws: descriptive (it doesn’t fit some salient features of the object), functional (whatever agents intend to do with that concept would work better if it was modified in such and such way), or normative, and even moral. According to Jiménez, there is a strong normative case for officials to adopt an operative concept of law, which would be positivistic.
- 59 Jiménez is aware that it is not obvious that officials would need a fully developed operative concept of law (Jiménez 2023: 364-365). As I have suggested all along, there are strong reasons to doubt it. Jiménez agrees that officials do not usually “adopt an articulate, explicit concept of law” (*ibid.*). They rather have an “inchoate picture”, an “image of law” that governs the way they apply and interpret the law. According to him, this “image of law” is what comparative lawyers have in mind when they try to go beyond black-letter law to excavate the cultural, ideological, and philosophical commitments²⁶ without which black-letter law cannot be fully understood (some, like Legrand, believe they can never be fully understood by outsiders such as comparativists). The idea, then, is that legal philosophers should try to make this image of the law more precise and more articulate by making it match the commitments of legal positivism. This is what Jiménez argues for (and makes a moral case for) in the remainder of his article.
- 60 I will not elaborate on the specific case that Jiménez makes for his brand of normative positivism, although I will say that if you accept his premises, he makes a pretty strong case. For instance, he suggests quite conclusively that if officials were to adopt a positivistic concept of law, they would do a better job at settling moral disagreements (which is, functionally, what law is supposed to do) than if they adopted a natural law concept of law, which would prompt them to replicate the moral disputes the law is meant to settle. They would, moreover, have more clarity over the distinction between two different situations, one in which the law runs out, thus prompting moral deliberation on the official’s part, and the other in which there is a law, one that the interpreter just doesn’t like for moral reasons.
- 61 My point is that although it was not his main goal, what makes Jiménez’s account particularly appealing is that it gives legal philosophy a purpose, a relevance for legal practice: *the law* would probably be better if officials adopted a specific concept of law tracking specific legal philosophical tenets. It bears noting that Jiménez does not fall prey to the confusion between law and the law. Legal philosophers writing about the “nature of law” usually try to give a foundational account of what law is, even though in so doing, they claim to be unearthing the features of shared concepts (see Raz 1994: 237; Raz 2009: 28-31). This is not in itself relevant for legal practice, as Jiménez agrees.

What is relevant is that, according to Jiménez, legal philosophers should try to modify and hone the *operative* concepts underlying officials' epistemic practices to make them match their own concept of law to some extent. But even if we assume that e.g., legal positivists are wrong about the "true" nature of law, as it were, there would still be a strong moral case for urging officials to adopt a positivistic operative concept of law. This would make legal philosophy relevant for legal practice, since it would aim at *changing* it.

- 62 I nevertheless remain unconvinced that it would make sense for officials and lawyers to adopt a concept of law tracking jurisprudential tenets (such as legal positivism or anti-positivism). Jiménez is completely right that members of the legal community (judges, lawyers, etc.) share an underlying, and often subconscious, "image of law", which varies from country to country. It is also the case that *legal philosophers* are, to some extent, influenced by this "image", especially when they have attended law school. This explains the mismatch between national or regional schools of legal philosophy: Anglo-American and Continental jurisprudence often seem to talk past each other (and so do the various national or regional traditions within Continental jurisprudence). This is because legal philosophies reflect, to some extent, this underlying "image of law", this inchoate concept of law that has been sedimented in the background of legal practices by centuries of legal education and legal ideologies. (This paper is probably no exception). However, legal philosophy, though influenced by these inchoate concepts, often aims to go beyond them, and sometimes to run counter to them. These "images of law" are quite often wrong or misguided, and the philosopher's job is precisely to resist them, rather than embrace them.
- 63 Moreover, a legal community's "image of law" is not wholly, if at all, congruent with the "concept of law" articulated by philosophers. Take Jiménez's formulation of "legal positivism" as a concept of law that judges ought to adopt: "legal facts are necessarily and exclusively grounded in social facts, which might require legal interpreters to engage in constrained moral reasoning".²⁷ This claim rests on technical philosophical concepts: "legal facts", "grounding", "constrained reasoning", etc. As I contended in the last section, these concepts aim at capturing *certain* aspects of legal practice, and they can be more or less successful depending on the criteria of success of all philosophical endeavours. But whatever our "image of law" is, it is about the first-order features of law, not about what the philosophical enterprise aims at capturing. Whatever features of law are important according to "our image of law" may prove, in some instances, wholly irrelevant for the articulation of a jurisprudential concept of law. Granted, our image of law often comprises a pre-theoretical account of what law is (*quid jus*) which, as we saw in the last section, explains why and how legal officials and practitioners identify their practice as a *legal* practice and themselves as *legal* officials and legal practitioners. But this inchoate pre-theoretical concept of law is usually interwoven with jurisdiction-specific cultural or ideological representations. For instance, our image of law often has to do with the *substance* of legal rules or with an *ideology* of the role of lawyers: one could say that a French lawyer's image of law, such as it is reflected, for instance, in the content of contract law or tort law, usually includes a moralistic, justice-oriented conception of what law is, because the word we use to say "law" is "le droit" (*jus, das Recht, il diritto*)—which, distinct as it is from "*lex*" (*la loi*), is infused with a certain ideology of justice (see Hart 2012: 208, and for a critique, Sandro 2022: 53). On the other hand, an American lawyer's image of law will be less justice-oriented as it will see law as a tool for facilitating and optimizing economic

transactions, which, again will be reflected in the content of tort law or contract law. (I am aware this is absolutely simplistic). So, when Thomas Grey or Richard Rorty claim that “pragmatism is the implicit working theory of most good lawyers” (Grey 1990: 1590; Rorty 1990: 1811), they are probably describing part of the “image of law” implicit in American legal practice, but this insight is not likely generalizable, let alone universalizable. And indeed, when comparativists discuss whether legal transplants are possible across distinct legal cultures (see the Watson/Kahn-Freund debate in the 1970s, especially Kahn-Freund 1974), they are precisely discussing whether the differences between the “images of law” underlying these cultures, makes it impossible to transplant *these* rules, with *this specific content*, from one system to another.

- 64 But none of this is congruent with what legal philosophers have been talking about: the fact that, e.g., the specific *content* of the law is deemed infused by French lawyers with a certain ideology of justice doesn’t mean that the French image of law is somehow anti-positivistic. This is because legal positivism was never about the specific content of legal rules—which varies from country to country—but about what grounds the existence of *all legal rules in all legal systems*. So, even if we assume that our “image of law” could somehow be reformed by philosophers, the salient (or salient enough) features in our image of the law still do not necessarily match the features that legal philosophers have found relevant for their own concept of law.
- 65 There certainly is a case²⁸ to be made that legal philosophers should pay more attention to these “images of the law”, which make up the deep conceptual structure of QJurA practices. This would entail being more sensitive to the data of comparative law, as well as experimental jurisprudence insofar as it purports to investigate folk concepts of law. But this in no way shows that legal philosophers could ever be in the business of *reforming* our image of the law because there will always remain, as a matter of material necessity, a gap between the philosopher’s concept of law and whatever folk concepts underlie our images of the law.
- 66 Does that mean that legal philosophy is irrelevant? No. All this means is that whatever relevance legal philosophy has does not come from its relevance for legal practice. Not only is the concept of law irrelevant for QJurAs, but there is also reason to doubt that legal philosophers could ever successfully prompt legal actors to adopt their favoured concept of law. So, the case for the relevance of legal philosophy cannot rest on its relevance for legal practice. It must rest on something else. Whatever that something else is, I leave for another occasion.

4 A short conclusion

- 67 In this paper I have tried to show that questions about what law is (as addressed by philosophers talking about the nature or the concept of law) and questions about what the law is (as addressed by legal practitioners and officials) are two independent questions. Although the way officials address and answer questions about what the law is is part of the stuff legal philosophers have been philosophizing about, whatever truths they discover about the nature/concept of law are irrelevant to the ascertainment of what the law is in a given jurisdiction, and therefore to the resolution of legal disputes. I have argued that failure to account for the difference between *quid jus* and the *quid juris* questions has led certain strains of contemporary legal philosophy to avoidable confusions or ambiguities. At the end of the day, Flaubert was right:

nobody knows what law is. But this doesn't prevent lawyers and officials from correctly ascertaining what the law is on this or that issue.

- 68 I leave open the question of the relevance of philosophical discourse on the nature or concept of law. Although some versions of normative positivism make a strong case for the relevance of such discourse for legal practice, I remain unconvinced that adopting a specific jurisprudential concept of law would change the way officials go about ascertaining what the law is in their jurisdiction. This is, however, no cause for pessimism or despair. General jurisprudence is often practiced by legal academics: it is only natural that they would try to make their field relevant by convincing their fellow lawyers (and themselves) that what they do is relevant for legal practice. Although legal philosophy cannot help lawyers do their jobs, it nevertheless enriches their worldview; it makes them question their underlying "images of law" and develop critical, argumentative, and rational skills. While not directly relevant for their practice, it nevertheless makes better lawyers out of them.

—**Acknowledgment.**— *A version of this paper was presented and discussed in the Special Workshop 8 "Legal Philosophy and Legal Practice", organised within the XXI World Congress of the International Association for the Philosophy of Law and Social Philosophy (IVR) held in Seoul, South Korea (7 to 12 July, 2024). The Workshop was organised as a part of the EU Horizon Project ALF - Advancing Cooperation on the Foundations of Law (project 101079177, financed by the European Union). Many thanks to all the participants for great feedback, especially Julieta Rábanos, Bojan Spaić, Michele Ubertone, Piero Mattei-Gentili and Kristin Albrecht. I would also like to thank the two anonymous reviewers, who pointed out several points in dire need of clarification.*

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alexy, R. (2021). *Law's Ideal Dimension*. Oxford University Press.
- Campbell, T. (1996). *The Legal Theory of Ethical Positivism*. Dartmouth.
- Carpentier, M. (2026). Against "Legal Facts". *Canadian Journal of Law & Jurisprudence*, 1-37. doi: 10.1017/cjlj.2025.10061
- Chiassoni, P. (2011). The Simple and Sweet Virtues of Analysis. A Plea for Hart's Metaphilosophy of Law. *Problema*, 5, 53-80.
- Coleman, J. (2001). *The Practice of Principle*. Oxford University Press.
- Coleman, Jules L., and O. Simchen. "Law." *Legal Theory*, 9(1), 1-42.
- Diamond, A. (2025). Lawfinding's Dilemma: Legal Formalism, or Judicial Neutrality. *Oregon Law Review*, 104, 117-172.
- Dickson, J. (2017). Why General Jurisprudence is Interesting. *Crítica*, 49, 11-40.

- Duarte, D. (2021). From Constitutional Discretion to the Positivist Weight Formula. In J.R. Sieckmann (Ed.), *Proportionality, Balancing, and Rights: Robert Alexy's Theory of Constitutional Rights* (pp. 11–48). Springer.
- Dworkin, R. (1986). *Law's Empire*. Harvard University Press.
- Dworkin, R. (2006). *Justice in Robes*. Harvard University Press.
- Dyrda, A. (2016). The epistemology of theoretical disagreement. In P. Banaś, A. Dyrda & T. Gizbert-Studnicki (Eds.), *Metaphilosophy of Law* (pp. 227–260). Hart Publishing.
- Dyrda, A. & Gizbert-Studnicki, T. (2022). Is the analysis of the concept of law a(n) (im)modest conceptual analysis? *Jurisprudence*, 13(3), 370–392.
- Dyzenhaus, D. & Taggart, M. (2009). Reasoned Decisions and Legal Theory. In D. Edlin (Ed.), *Common Law Theory* (pp. 134–168). Cambridge University Press.
- Finnis, J. (2011). *Natural Law and Natural Rights* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Finnis, J. (2025). Joseph Raz. *Biographical Memoirs of Fellows of the British Academy*, 22, 307–341.
- Enoch, D. (2019). Is General Jurisprudence Interesting? In D. Plunkett, S.J. Shapiro & K. Toh, (Eds.), *Dimensions of Normativity: New Essays on Metaethics and Jurisprudence* (pp. 65–86). Oxford University Press.
- Gardner, J. (2001). Legal Positivism: 5 1/2 Myths. *American Journal of Jurisprudence*, 46(1), 199–227.
- Giudice, M. (2015). *Understanding the Nature of Law*. Elgar.
- Grey, T. (1990). Hear the Other Side" Wallace Stevens and Pragmatist Legal Theory. *Southern California Law Review*, 63(6), 1569–1595.
- Hart, H. L. A. (1983). *Essays in Jurisprudence dans Philosophy*. Oxford University Press
- Hart, H. L. A. (2012). *The Concept of Law* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Jiménez, F. (2023). Legal Positivism for Legal Officials. *Canadian Journal of Law and Jurisprudence*, 36(3), 359–286.
- Kahn-Freund, O. (1974). The Uses and Misuses of Comparative Law. *Modern Law Review*, 37(1), 1–27.
- Kant, I. (1991). *Metaphysics of Morals* (M. Gregor, Trans.). Cambridge University Press. (Original work published 1797)
- Kornhauser, L. (2004). Governance Structures, Legal Systems, and the Concept of Law. *Chicago-Kent Law Review*, 79(2) 355–381.
- Kornhauser, L. (2015). Doing Without the Concept of Law. Unpublished paper available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2640605
- Kramer, M. (2003). Review of *Evaluation and Legal Theory* by Julie Dickson. *Cambridge Law Journal*, 62(1), 210–215.
- Leiter, B. (2003). Beyond the Hart-Dworkin Problem: The Methodology Debate in Jurisprudence. *American Journal of Jurisprudence*, 48 (1), 17–51.
- Levenbook, B. B. (2015). Dworkin's Theoretical Disagreement Argument. *Philosophy Compass*, 15(1), 1–9.
- Marmor, A. (2013). Farewell to Conceptual Analysis (in Jurisprudence). In W. Waluchow & S. Sciaraffa (Eds.), *Philosophical Foundations of the Nature of Law*. Oxford University Press.

- Murphy, L. (2014). *What Makes Law. An Introduction to the Philosophy of Law*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nye, H. (2017). A Critique of the Concept–Nature Nexus in Joseph Raz’s Methodology. *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 37(1), 48–74.
- Nye, H. (2022). Does Law ‘Exist’? Eliminativism in Legal Philosophy. *Washington University Jurisprudence Review*, 15(1), 29–78.
- Patterson, D. (2016). Can We Please Stop Doing This? By the Way, Postema Was Right. In P. Banaś, A. Dyrda & T. Gizbert-Studnicki (Eds.), *Metaphilosophy of Law* (pp. 49–64). Hart Publishing.
- Posner, R. (1997). *Law and Legal Theory in England and America*. Oxford University Press.
- Postema, G. (1998). Jurisprudence as Practical Philosophy. *Legal Theory*, 4(3), 329–357.
- Priel, D. (2011). The Place of Legitimacy in Legal Theory. *McGill Law Journal*, 57(1), 1–35.
- Ramirez Ludeña, L. (2016). Legal Disagreements. *Revus – Journal for constitutional theory and philosophy of law*, 28, 11–32.
- Raz, J. (1994). *Ethics in the Public Domain*. Oxford University Press.
- Raz, J. (2007). Teoría y conceptos. Réplica a Alexy y Bulygin. In J. Raz, R. Alexy & E. Bulygin, *Una discusión sobre la teoría del derecho*. Marcial Pons.
- Raz, J. (2009). *Between Authority and Interpretation*. Oxford University Press.
- Rorty, R. (1990). The Banality of Pragmatism and the Poetry of Justice. *Southern California Law Review*, 63(6), 1811–1819.
- Rosen, A. (2018). Law as an Interactive Kind: On the Concept and the Nature of Law. *Canadian Journal of Law and Jurisprudence*, 31(1), 125–149.
- Sacco, R. (1991). Legal Formants: A Dynamic Approach to Comparative Law. *American Journal of Comparative Law*, 39(1), 1–34.
- Sandro, P. (2022). *The Making of Constitutional Democracy*. Hart Publishing.
- Schauer, F. (2012). On the Nature of the Nature of Law. *Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie*, 98(4), 457–467.
- Sciaraffa, S. (2011). Hermeneutic Concepts and Immodest Conceptual Analysis of the Law. Unpublished paper available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1905836.
- Shapiro, S. (2011). *Legality*. Harvard University Press.
- Smith, D. (2010). Theoretical Disagreement and the Semantic Sting. *OJLS*, 30(4), 635–661.
- Spaic B. (2014). On the Essential Contestedness of the Concept of Law. *Synthesis Philosophica*, 57(1), 175–189.
- Tamanaha, B. (2017). Necessary and Universal Truths About Law? *Ratio Juris*, 30(1), 3–24.
- Waldron, J. (2001). Normative (or Ethical) Positivism. In J. Coleman (Ed.), *Hart’s Postscript: Essays on the Postscript to ‘The Concept of Law’* (pp. 410–433). Oxford University Press.
- Watson, B. (2023). How to Answer Dworkin’s Argument from Theoretical Disagreement Without Attributing Confusion or Disingenuity to Legal Officials. *Canadian Journal of Law and Jurisprudence*, 36(1), 215–240.

NOTES

1. Translation modified. I think it is high time we stopped translating “Recht” (as in *Rechtslehre*) as “Right” in the Kantian or Hegelian contexts—except of course when the author is talking about *Rechte*, that is (subjective) *rights*. That Kant has a highly moralized concept of law does not mean that he is not talking about law but about some queer metaphysical entity called “the Right”.
2. See for instance, Richard Posner: “I have nothing against philosophical speculation. But one would like it to have some pay-off; something ought to turn on the answer to the question ‘What is law?’... Nothing does turn on it. I go further: the central task of analytic jurisprudence is, or at least ought to be, not to answer the question ‘What is law?’ but to show that it should not be asked, because it only confuses matters” (Posner 1997: 3).
3. I do not intend to get into the debates about whether legal philosophy is interesting or not (Enoch 2019; Dickson 2017), which is at best an orthogonal question here. Enoch questions whether law and legal practice have philosophically interesting features, that is, whether the kind of normativity displayed by law (and in the law) makes it ripe for philosophical treatment (in contrast with other kinds of “formal” normativity such as rules of etiquette). My question in this paper is, in a way, the converse: is legal philosophy relevant for legal practice?
4. See, among polemicists against essentialism, Leiter 2003; Tamanaha 2017; Patterson 2016; Schauer 2012; Nye 2017.
5. I will treat expressions such as “it is the law that X ought to φ ” and “the law requires X to φ ” as extensionally equivalent.
6. See Priel 2011: 29-30; Dyzenhaus & Taggart 2009: 162.
7. Finnis 2025: 334-335. On the relevance of the distinction between law and the law for Finnis’ work, see Kramer 2003: 212.
8. I am going to be expeditious in my treatment of Dworkin’s argument from theoretical disagreement because my point is not exegetical. See, in the recent literature, Dyrda 2016; Ramirez Ludeña 2016; Watson 2023.
9. 115 N.Y. 506 (1889). The question in this case was whether a person who murders his grandfather can inherit from the deceased. The New York Court of Appeals held that although no statute explicitly barred the grandson from inheriting, the principle according to which no man may profit from his own wrong nevertheless defeated his claim.
10. In the Dworkinian sense. I am not claiming that interpretive disputes revolve around disagreements about empirical facts. My only point is that *pace* Dworkin, interpretive disagreements are not disagreements about the “grounds of law” but about the meaning of statutes and other legal provisions (which is precisely what Dworkin calls “empirical disagreement”).
11. It bears noting that in his 2003 article with Ori Simchen (Coleman and Simchen 2003: 5), Coleman distinguishes not two, but eight questions: (1) What is law? (2) What is a law? (3) What is the law? (4) What is the nature of law? (5) What is the meaning of law? (6) What is the concept of law? (7) What is the meaning of the concept of law? (8) What is the meaning of “law”? Coleman and Simchen focus on (8), which is about the semantics and meta-semantics of the word “law”, which, *pace* Dworkin, is not usually germane to general jurisprudence. For them, (5) and (7) are ill-formed, and (4) and (6) are interchangeable with (1). There remain three irreducible, fundamental questions: (1), (2) and (3). They insist that (1) and (3) need to be separated, although Dworkin conflates them. They do not take any position regarding (2); nor does the present paper.
12. Unlike Nye I am not an eliminativist about “law” because I do not think that asking what law is necessarily commits one to endorsing a metaphysical conception of what the essential properties of law are. As I indicated in the introduction there is a whole range of meta-

philosophical options for ascertaining how the “nature” and/or the “concept” of an X should be conceived. But this is beyond the point.

13. The question of what ontological kind law is, is of course disputed. I will assume law is a social kind, rather than e.g., an artifact kind, but this can be obviously disputed.

14. I talk about criteria of “membership” rather than validity because “validity” is ambiguous. I will only talk about a single dimension of validity, according to which “a norm is (legally) valid” =_{def} “a norm belongs to the legal system”. I will sometimes use “criteria of legality” to refer to the same thing.

15. For instance, Finnis’ disagreement with positivists does not specifically concerns their account of QJurAs – according to which morality is not part of the criteria of legality or membership (see Finnis 2011: 363-368). This led Hart to claim, not without reason, that “Finnis’s flexible interpretation of natural law is in many respects complementary to rather than a rival of positivist legal theory” (Hart 1983: 10).

16. [2017] UKSC 5.

17. [1968] 2 S.A. 284.

18. [1969] 1 A.C. 645 at 668.

19. See eg *North Sea Continental Shelf* (Judgment) [1969] ICJ Rep 3.

20. See e.g., *Statement from President Joe Biden on the Equal Rights Amendment*, 17 Jan 2025.

21. See e.g., *Roper v. Simmons*, 543 U.S. 551 (2005) (Scalia J dissenting); *Glossip v. Gross*, 576 U.S. 863 (2015) (Breyer J dissenting).

22. U.S. Constitution, 2nd Amdt: “A well regulated Militia, being necessary to the security of a free State, the right of the people to keep and bear Arms, shall not be infringed.”

23. *New York State Rifle & Pistol Association, Inc. v. Bruen*, 597 U.S. 1 (2022)

24. To be clear, Alexy does not claim that his weight formula may be used by participants to settle balancing disputes. To the contrary: it is merely an analytical tool.

25. Among an enormous literature, see Campbell 1996; Postema 1998; Waldron 2001.

26. He cites, in particular, the work of William Ewald, Catherine Valcke and Pierre Legrand (See Jiménez 2023: 365). One should add Rodolfo Sacco’s theory of “formants” and “cryptotypes” (Sacco 1991).

27. I have criticized this formulation as not really capturing what legal positivism has classically been about (Carbut rehearsing my critique would be beyond the point here).

28. I had actually tried to make such a case in a now-deleted fourth section of this paper. I will have to reserve these developments for another occasion.

ABSTRACTS

Immanuel Kant warned against confusing the question of what law is (*quid jus*) and what the law is in a given jurisdiction (*quid juris*). This paper tries to revive this long-forgotten admonition. Some jurists seem to presuppose that lawyers and officials are in the business of investigating what law is, which leads to regrettable confusions. Moreover, the philosophical concept of law (*quid jus*) has no relevance for law-ascertainment practices (*quid juris*), even though *quid juris* ascertainties are part of the practice legal philosophers philosophize about. Legal disagreements are of various kinds, but none of their solutions involve any kind of recourse to philosophical claims about the nature of law. This, in turns, raises the question: if legal

philosophy (insofar as it purports to be about the nature or the concept of law) is irrelevant to law-ascertainment practices, what is it good for?

Quid jus ali quid juris? Immanuel Kant je opozarjal pred zamenjevanjem vprašanja, kaj je pravo (*quid jus*), z vprašanjem, kaj lahko izpeljemo iz določenega pravnega reda (*quid juris*). Ta prispevek skuša obuditi to dolgo pozabljeno opozorilo. Zdi se namreč, da nekateri pravni teoretiki predpostavljajo, da se pravniki in uradniki v prvi vrsti ukvarjajo z vprašanjem, kaj je pravo, to pa vodi v obžalovanja vredno zmedo. Poleg tega filozofski pojem prava (*quid jus*) nima nobenega pomena pri odgovorih na drugo vprašanje (*quid juris*), čeprav so ti odgovori del pravne prakse, o kateri razmišljajo pravni filozofi. Poznamo več vrst pravnih nesoglasij, vendar nobena rešitev teh nesoglasij ne vključuje sklicevanja na filozofske trditve o naravi prava. Zato se odpira naslednje vprašanje: če je filozofija prava (z obravnavo narave ali pojma prava) nepomembna za pravno prakso, čemu sploh služi?

INDEX

motslessl narava prava, pojem prava, pravna nesoglasja, prakse ugotavljanja prava, eliminativizem, relevantnost pravne filozofije

Keywords: nature of law, concept of law, legal disagreements, law-ascertainment practices, eliminativism, relevance of legal philosophy

AUTHOR

MATHIEU CARPENTIER

 IDREF : <https://idref.fr/179740016>

 ORCID : <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0834-9817>

 VIAF : <http://viaf.org/viaf/313566702>

 ISNI : <https://isni.org/isni/0000000444727703>

 BnF : <http://data.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb169434366>

Professor of public law, University Toulouse 1 Capitole (France). **ORCID:** 0009-0009-0834-9817. **E-mail:** mathieu.carpentier@ut-capitole.fr